

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COMPONENTS OF CONTENT STANDARDS

Ibrahimov F.,
professor

*Shaki Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University,
Azerbaijan, Shaki*

Abdullayeva G.,
associate professor

*Shaki Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University,
Azerbaijan, Shaki*

Kerimova M.

*Shaki Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University,
Azerbaijan, Shaki*

Abstract

The article argues the relevance of the topic, emphasizes that knowledge, skills and habits are the main components of education, comments on the schematic description of the relationship between these components in scientific sources, clarifies the dialectical unity, development and functions of knowledge, skills and habits. It has been shown that consciousness, which is "impersonal", free from subjective factors and relatively independent of material activity, is really expressed in the form of knowledge.

The work provides an interpretation of the knowledge included in the training material in groups, focuses on the hierarchical arrangement of cognitive skills, looks at different classifications of intellectual skills, reveals the peculiarities of their formation in students, introduces effective ways of learning. In general, it is stated that when students have a clear idea of psychological processes, they do not shy away from difficulties when they believe in the possibilities of their thinking, they think and try to solve the problem, even if they fail.

Keywords: content standard, component, intellectual skills, factorological, procedural, conceptual, metacognitive knowledge.

Relevance of the research topic

From the analysis of scientific sources and materials collected on the activities of teachers in real pedagogical processes, it is clear that there are different approaches to making students' learning activities adequate for scientific activities, but the results are not successful. There are many reasons for this shortcoming, including insufficient disclosure of the scientific-theoretical, pedagogical and technological aspects of knowledge, skills, habits, developmental dialectics and functions as components of the unit, which are components of content standards. Despite the above, we claim the relevance of the study of the subject.

Interpretation of research materials

First of all, the training serves to equip students with the basics of science, to acquire knowledge, skills and habits for their mental and practical activities. Knowledge, skills and habits are key components of education. In particular, knowledge is a key, leading component of learning. It is well known that it reflects the generalized experience of mankind, the reflection of facts, rules and results, laws, theories that belong to science in various spheres of life. [1; 111]

Skills and habits acquired in the teaching process are also necessary components of education. For example, reading, writing, arithmetic, labor, solving mental and practical problems, etc.

We would like to dwell on the concept of skills and habits, as there have been conflicting opinions in the literature recently about their interpretation. Some scientific sources emphasize that in pedagogy, "skill" means a "Habit" is a kind of automation, the correct,

error-free execution of a skill acquired as a result of many repetitions and efforts. [5;259]. It follows that "skill" is formed on the basis of knowledge, and "habit" is formed on the basis of "skill". In our opinion, the following interpretation, which has a place in Russian psychological thought, is interesting in terms of understanding these concepts at a more acceptable level: Training is a type of activity, the direct purpose of which is to master certain information, actions, forms of behavior. In other words, the active process of directing human activity and behavior to assimilate the social experience of mankind is called learning. Such specific activities of the subject with the purpose of learning include: 1) the acquisition of information about the necessary, important properties of the world for the successful organization of this or that type of ideal and practical activity (the product of this process is knowledge); 2) mastering the ways and operations that make up that activity (habits are the product of this process); 3) to master the rules of using the mentioned information to correctly select and control the ways and operations appropriate to the conditions of the issue and the forthcoming purpose (the end product of this process is skills). [4;192]

Recently, there has been an opinion that "habit" is not based on skills, but "habit" is a component of skills. Some didactics and psychologists agree. For example, V.A. Onishchuk, referring to the theory put forward by P.Y. Galper in psychology, writes: Ability - the ability to perform complex, complex movements. Habits are formed on the basis of knowing the rules of execution

of actions ... Skill is a creative activity on its basis. [12; 21]

It is difficult to agree with such an interpretation of the issue. Although this interpretation is supported by many psychologists, it confuses practitioners, especially teachers. There is no reason to deny that in the pedagogical process, the ability is formed at one level, and the third level rises at a more complex level. How to talk about automated actions (habits), even if the student knows how to do it, he is not able to solve it in practice. Are there few cases in the learning process when a student who knows how to solve a problem theoretically is not able to solve it in practice? If the habit is based on practice, what can a student work on without being able to do it? V.A. Onishchuk does not agree with the scheme "Knowledge - simple skills, habits - complex skills." [5; 259]

In our opinion, this scheme has a certain meaning. Simple skills are formed on the basis of knowledge, give rise to habits, and on the basis of the latter, complex, high-level skills are formed. For example, on the basis of elementary writing skills, the habit of writing competently, the habit of literate speech is formed, on the basis of which the student is able to express his opinion competently, write essays, official letters, articles, etc. Gains complex skills such as writing. But this is not the end of the matter.

Undoubtedly, complex skills also contain elements of creative movements, which gradually rise to a higher level, rise to the level of creative activity, and finally, it also becomes a kind of habit. In our schools, are there few educated, editing and oral students who write meaningful poems, describe social and natural events in a creative and artistic way, and appear in the youth press with their own articles? Similar situations occur in the field of engineering, music, fine and applied arts, as well as in the teaching of mathematics, physics and chemistry. All this shows that the relationship between skill and habit is more appropriate to express in the following scheme, more scientifically sound: *knowledge - simple skills - habits - complex skills - creative actions*. [5; 260-261]

All this also shows that when talking about skills and habits as a component of the educational function of training, it is not enough to focus only on the simple teaching skills and habits acquired. It should also cover the application of theoretical information in practice, the skills and habits acquired in the system of mental and practical activities necessary for a creative person. It should not be forgotten that it is also a matter of instilling creative skills in students. Among the various forms of consciousness that make up the human spiritual world, knowledge is the most foreign to him. In particular, knowledge that is not directly related to the person himself, his personal life and destiny! In fact, knowledge is not a reflection of a person's own life, but of the objective reality that surrounds him. The form of consciousness, which reflects a person's personal life and is a reflection of his own events, is already expressed in another way - it is considered a memory. Memories can be "bitter" or "sweet", "pale" or "colorful", and can repeat a person's feelings over time. Knowledge, on the other hand, is lifeless and neutral,

not directly related to human emotions, and is alien to man in this sense. [9; 258]

In real spiritual life, neither emotional images are completely isolated from concepts, nor concepts from emotional images. Emotion and rationality are always united and complement each other. However, both feelings and imaginations, as well as concepts and judgments, have a certain relative independence, and it is through this independence that it is possible to distinguish them and evaluate them as different stages of cognition. [9; 260]

It should be noted that there is no need to remember each of the recurring events in all their specificity and detail, and this is not possible. Because a large part of human life is made up of recurring events. Therefore, details are discarded, the emotional image is freed from inconspicuous features, the main recurring features are generalized - concepts are formed and the event is interpreted by a system of concepts.

It is possible to think only with concepts, it is impossible to be influenced by them. Assimilation of ordinary life events, which are not related to a person's specialization, professional activity, arises from daily necessities and are common to all people, corresponds to a form of cognition called "ordinary consciousness". Along with forms of professional cognition, such as scientific cognition, artistic cognition, and philosophical thinking, ordinary consciousness is also one of the important ways of perceiving reality. But there is an important qualitative difference. Ordinary consciousness is not a field of professional cognition and forms the basis of cognitive activity of all people. The product of ordinary consciousness is ordinary knowledge. As the scope of human activity expands, this knowledge goes beyond "ordinary knowledge." Relatively different kinds of knowledge emerge, which form a kind of core of human activity. This knowledge no longer serves that person directly, but through society, as a member of society. Knowledge that is already alien to man becomes even more alien because it goes beyond his personal sphere of life. [9; 260]

In our opinion, it would be more accurate to clarify the nature of knowledge by looking at when its history began. In the process of interacting with nature, in order to satisfy his necessary material needs, man first begins to perceive nature as a continuation of himself, and then as a different, opposite side to himself. As long as man cannot separate himself from nature, his perceptions of nature are limited to the senses and the senses. This feeling, which is a historically primitive reflection of the human-nature relationship, although the landscapes have a certain dynamics, does not adequately reflect the reality, as it were, in its objective content. The transition to social-natural relations takes place in parallel with the transition from syncretic thinking to logical thinking. Society does not encompass the biological existence of human beings and does not act as a part of nature, but as an independent entity that exists in parallel with it and, therefore, can be compared with it when necessary. Therefore, as a member of society, as a social being, as an individual, human consciousness reflects nature outside of man, in a "dehumanized" state,

as it really is (meaning only scientific truth). The history of knowledge also begins from this time.

Scientific sources rightly state that consciousness, which is "impersonal", free from subjective factors and relatively independent of material activity, is really expressed in the form of knowledge. Knowledge comes from memory, impressions, emotional images, unconscious acts of consciousness, and so on. in contrast, it emerges as a result of logical thinking and is expressed in terms and concepts. The history of knowledge coincides not with the history of any form of consciousness, but with the history of logical thinking. [9;266]

There are different classifications of knowledge in the relevant literature. Thus, scientific, historical, abstract, concrete, analytical, empirical, practical, intellectual, etc. distinguish types of knowledge. [7; 111]

The knowledge included in the training material can be divided into three groups: generalized knowledge, generalized methods of action, specific knowledge. The first group includes concepts, laws, principles, rules, etc. includes. Knowledge belonging to this group can be acquired in the following ways: a) understanding, etc. memorize without understanding the content and essence, b) ready result, learning in the form of generalization, or rather, understanding, etc. disclosure of the content by the teacher or with the help of the textbook: c) independent access.

The second group includes knowledge of the nature of objects and events in the real world, as well as the methods and techniques used to understand the regularities between the relevant concepts, laws and rules. The knowledge included in this group should be didactically appropriate in each case. Thus, one concept, rule, law can be mastered through the solution of the problem of learning, another explained - through reproduction.

The third group includes facts, terms, dates, names, quantities, events, and so on. includes. The knowledge belonging to this group is not generalizing, it just requires memorization. The third group of knowledge, as a rule, is not acquired through problem-based learning. [6; 447-454]

This knowledge can be interpreted as follows: 1) Declarative knowledge - knowledge of individual information: knowledge of terminology; know the specific element and details. 2) Conceptual knowledge - consists of an information system: knowledge of classifications and concepts; know the principles and generalizations; know the theory, models and structures. 3) Procedural knowledge - knowledge of methods and their use: knowledge of specific skills and algorithms; know concrete methods and techniques; know the criteria for determining when an appropriate method will be used.

The knowledge component can include "metacognitive knowledge". Metacognitive knowledge - knowledge of thinking processes and information, their effective use: strategic knowledge; knowledge of cognitive tasks, including relevant contextual and conditional knowledge; self-awareness. [8; 37-42]

Habit is a more objective phenomenon than a phenomenon of consciousness, or rather, an objectified, differentiated consciousness. Just as tools-techniques,

machines-techniques are in fact the distinction of scientific-practical knowledge, the designer's imagination in things beyond man, as well as habit-technique is the distinction of practical knowledge in man's own hands. [9; 278].

Habit is a more objective phenomenon than a phenomenon of consciousness, or rather, an objectified, differentiated consciousness. Just as tools-techniques, machines-techniques are in fact the distinction of scientific-practical knowledge, the designer's imagination in things beyond man, as well as habit-technique is the distinction of practical knowledge in man's own hands. Indeed, at each subsequent stage of development of technology, machines appear that replace the previous function of the hand, "mastering" the practical skills of man. As the structure of a complex machine includes various components that replace one or another human function, it becomes more automated. Man himself, on the other hand, is becoming increasingly free from the features of being a living machine gun, and is more and more acting as a conscious being, engaged in creative work. If primitive labor is always based only on the activation of the same habit, and there is no obvious component of consciousness, the more complex forms of labor imply the multiplicity of such habits through open consciousness, as if on the basis of a certain program. Such complex labor cannot be replaced by a simpler machine, there is a need for an "executor" provided with "artificial intelligence". It should be noted here that it is impossible to create a single, universal technical carrier of artificial intelligence. Only special machines that perform individual intellectual functions can be developed. That is, when each type of cybernetic machine is developed, it is adapted to a pre-conceived direction of activity and can only "work in that field of research". Of course, cars have a certain relative independence and the opportunity to vote. Due to a change in circumstances and position, one program is replaced by another. In some respects, artificial intelligence has a number of advantages over natural intelligence. A number of mental operations, which are impossible for natural intelligence, are easily performed by machines. We must not forget that natural intelligence is universal, that is, the performance of completely different quality intellectual operations is in principle possible for the same human brain. (see for more information: [9; 257-288])

The hierarchical arrangement of cognitive abilities can be interpreted as follows, and the analysis of the research materials obtained shows that it is useful from the point of view of its application in practice: Comprehension level - includes three categories of learning objectives: translation, translation (for example, translating an assignment from a practical language into a mathematical language); interpretation (for example, the ability to explain a mathematical solution in practical language); extrapolation (attribution of knowledge acquired in a certain field to another field, similar situations). The level of application implies the formation of students' ability to apply knowledge in practical situations. It can also be described in the following sub-levels: application of concepts; application of methods; application of algorithms. Level of analysis - implies

educational goals in the following categories: analysis of elements (separation or fragmentation); analysis of relations (relationships) (creation, proof of established links, dependencies between elements); analysis of principles (systematization of elements). Level of synthesis - the purpose of education, which forms the ability to determine the relationship between the individual elements produced in the process of analysis and to draw general conclusions from them: synthesis of ideas (for example, the search for solutions to a problem); synthesis of methods (preparation of a plan for solving the problem, determining the sequence of operations); synthesis of structures (formation of functions, sets, groups). Assessment level - involves the development of diagnostic skills, critical thinking and has the following categories: assessment based on internal judgment and knowledge (with evidence, proof, logic); assessment based on external criteria (standards, norms and rules).

It should also be noted that content standards are divided into cognitive, emotional and psychomotor skills in terms of performance. These skills are hierarchically arranged in taxonomies according to their level of development. It should be noted that there are verbs that express all stages of taxonomy (cognitive, emotional, psychomotor), which are considered suitable for education. Verbs are a very important indicator of skill expression. The verb reflects what stage of the taxonomy the skill belongs to.

There are different nomenclatures and classifications of skills that have a place in scientific sources. For example, let's take a step back and say that we think the learning process that includes STEAM is more creative and fun. On a logical basis, it is to be hoped that learners who are exposed to the effects of a cognitive or technological process that includes this subsystem will be able to innovate in the future. In this natural process, they use a variety of fields: mathematics and other exact sciences, engineering, design, digital devices and technology. STEAM is a relatively independent or dominant positional system with a universal practical orientation that allows students to perform any complex task, in which learners put their knowledge into practice. The cognitive or technological process that includes this subsystem is useful and necessary for every modern school. STEAM's special place in the training substrate allows students to learn creatively using 21st century skills such as problem solving. "The 4C skills of the 21st century are collaboration, creativity, critical thinking and communication, which are the perfect classification of skills, and they are an important component of a rapidly changing workforce and human success in society." (For more information, see: [https://525.az/?name=xeber&news_id=132946]).

Intellectual skills have a special place among the skills that schoolchildren must become subjects. Let's look at the issue in a broader area, and when the time comes, let's choose a point of view for the student in terms of activity and communication. Suppose that the mental operations (analysis, composition, etc.) are well formed, but he does not know the rules of working on the book, or a good question comes to mind, but he has difficulty in formulating it. There are many such facts

in school practice. Their analysis allows us to draw an important conclusion: the student must have the necessary intellectual skills to realize their intellectual potential, to purposefully regulate cognitive activity, it should be noted that Professor A.A. Alizadeh emphasizes that in the psychological and pedagogical literature, these skills are sometimes described in a broader sense as mental labor skills or teaching skills. In our opinion, it is not bad to remember the wise words of R. Descartes: "It is not enough to have a good mind, the main thing is to apply it well." [2; 59-60]

Various studies clearly show that students who lag behind in learning are characterized by extremely low levels of intellectual ability. [11; 110]. The main function of intellectual abilities is related to the externalization of intellectual operations: the content of cognitive activity is conditioned by intellectual operations, and their realization in the process of activity depends directly on the level of intellectual abilities. [11; 300]

Intellectual skills are numerous. Their different classifications are known in psychology and pedagogy. Given the research conducted in this area, especially the classification of N.A. Menchinskaya, intellectual abilities can be divided into the following groups: general intellectual skills (planning, book work, self-control); intellectual skills necessary for the organization of mental activity (to distinguish the main idea in the text, to divide the text into parts according to the meaning, to compare events, etc.); special intellectual skills (they reflect the characteristics of a subject, for example, cartographic or graphic skills). [11; 37-39]

İntellektual bacarıqların daha bir təsnifatı da maraqlıdır. I. Untun's classification distinguishes the following types: skills related to the perception of educational material (reading, observation, listening skills); ability to make logical operations with teaching material (assignment of important, comparison, ability to draw conclusions, etc.); creative skills (ability to build a composition, etc.). [2: 60]

Based on our experience, we can emphasize that intellectual skills are one of the fundamental issues in the learning process. Their formation in students has its own peculiarities. During the early school years, new mental qualities appear: an internal plan of activity is formed, mental processes gradually become independent, reflection is formed. On this basis, there are favorable conditions for the formation of general intellectual skills in the classroom, especially planning and self-monitoring skills. As the student's social experience expands, he or she gradually acquires the skills to work on the book, mastering the technology of reading teaching materials, speaking the content, and systematizing. The analysis of scientific sources leads to the conclusion that starting from V-VI, especially VII-VIII grades, they should pay consistent attention to the formation of general intellectual skills. In the context of the scientific and technological revolution, library and bibliographic skills play an important role in the effective use of scientific, scientific and popular literature, encyclopedias, explanatory dictionaries and periodicals, and in more detailed mastering of teaching materials. The analysis of scientific sources leads to the conclusion that starting from V-VI, especially VII-VIII

grades, they should pay consistent attention to the formation of general intellectual skills. In the context of the scientific and technological revolution, library and bibliographic skills play an important role in the effective use of scientific, scientific and popular literature, encyclopedias, explanatory dictionaries and periodicals, and in more detailed mastering of teaching materials.

The importance of general intellectual skills is clear. Advanced teachers focus on instilling in their students the wisdom of their experiences. While this in itself is gratifying, one aspect is undoubtedly unfortunate: the lack of study of general intellectual skills, on the one hand, classes and, on the other hand, the system and content of individual subjects, has a negative impact on students' scientific and methodological development. shows the effect. The intellectual skills necessary for the organization of mental activity, it seems, need to be distinguished. This issue, which is of great importance in itself, began to be understood in the same way in the 19th century. Prominent psychologists and educators of the time advised children to "teach reading", and made it one of the main tasks of the school to develop in students the skills necessary for the effective organization of their mental activities.

In the twentieth century, the importance of this issue has not diminished, but increased. Psychological (and pedagogical) research has identified experimental facts that explain the characteristics of the conditions for the formation of intellectual abilities. The call to "teach students to read" was gradually concretized on their basis: in the "Psychology" textbooks of the 30s and 40s of the last century, especially in the 50s and 60s, students-future teachers were already acquainted with the following effective ways of learning: 1. Setting goals; 2. Understanding; 3. Independent work; 4. Imagination; 5. Do not tell a story "in your own words"; 6. Importance of repetitions; 7. Division of repetitions; 8. Memory during learning; 9. Complete and partial learning; 10. When should we study?

All of these rules reflected the concept of traditional learning (read: memory): their main line was the strength and accuracy of memory. Although the rules referred to "understanding" and "imagining", these two rules did not change their essence and were interpreted only in the traditional way - in terms of memory. In the textbook "Psychology" (Baku, 1968) the essence of the methods of "effective learning of teaching material" was explained as follows: "In order to remember the perceived material, for example, the training material, as sufficiently strong, accurate and long-lasting, it is necessary to repeat it enough, in other words, to learn it. The strength and accuracy of memorization depend on the organization of learning".

As Professor A.A. Alizadeh emphasized, in the conditions of the scientific and technological revolution, these issues again manifested themselves in all their severity. The results of the unlimited abundance of information were obvious: the program material was increasing day by day. The volume of textbooks was rapidly expanding. New diseases of the century, such as information neurosis, were spreading to the world of

children. It was difficult to read on its own. The problem of "teaching children to read" again appeared in all its severity, but this problem was analyzed in a broader context - in the context of mental culture, mental culture, culture of thinking. In the 70s of the last century, new paradigms were already forming in the psychology of learning. In this case, the rules we have considered have already lost their former value. That is why the new "Psychology" textbooks of the 70's rejected "Effective Ways of Learning". These textbooks described the intellectual skills necessary for the organization of mental activity in a new way: they were expressed in the sense of purposeful perception, rational mastery, effective thinking. In this sense, two aspects attracted more attention: on the one hand, effective rules of learning are no longer limited to the concept of one-sided memory, issues are considered in the direction of mastery, on the other hand, the functions of perception and thinking are explained, they are "purposeful", "rational", "effective" were analyzed by dimensions. [2; 62-63]

How can you teach these rules to your students? The generalizations on the materials obtained from the analysis of scientific sources lead to the conclusion that in modern times there are two clear directions in the field of formation of intellectual abilities.

The first direction involves the formation of intellectual skills in students through special tasks. These tasks are based on the principle of modeling the structure of various intellectual abilities. As students complete them, they will be able to determine the purpose of their work, systematize teaching materials in this regard, independently collect material, write essays, and so on. acquire intellectual skills such as From the point of view of the principle of developmental training, this way is considered effective. However, in order to use it purposefully, the system and content of intellectual skills in classes and subjects must be thoroughly developed.

The second direction. In the process of developing intellectual skills with specific tasks, the teacher inevitably encounters a fundamental question: To what extent do students know the characteristics of their cognitive activity? The question itself is extremely relevant. Although we consider this issue in the direction of the formation of intellectual abilities, it should be noted that it has a broader meaning. This applies equally to both thought processes and intellectual abilities. Self-awareness has always been a topical issue in world philosophy, psychology and pedagogy. They approached the self-perception of a person from the point of view of personality, sought its roots in the formation of a person's perception of his "I", and did not appreciate the understanding of the features of his mental world, world of thought, cognitive processes.

"Logic Games", the author of L. Carroll's famous tale "Alice in Wonderland", which introduced children to the original graphic solution of syllogisms and syllables, was published in the 80s of the XIX century. In the twentieth century, various authors continued this tradition. Valuable books such as D. Poyyan's "How to solve the problem" (M., 1957), A.A. Ivy's "The art of right thinking" (M., 1990) were published. Experience

has clearly shown that students who study relevant books have a better understanding of themselves and are more interested in the characteristics of multifaceted cognitive activities. Lakin məktəb təcrübəsində idrak fəaliyyətinin psixologiyası öyrənilməmiş, şagirdlərin yaddaşının və ya təfəkkürünün xüsusiyyətləri ilə maraqlansalar da, onların maraqları öz-özünə təmin edilmir və zəifləyirdi. [2; 63]

In contemporary American psychology, this issue is given great importance and is studied as a meta-cognitive system. It has been established that as children develop, they develop certain ideas about cognitive processes. They begin to regulate their mental activity. How do these qualities manifest themselves in students and how can they be developed systematically? Flaywell studied and described in detail some of the functions of the meta-concept. Among them are: problem statement and identification of possible solutions; know what cognitive process is necessary to solve the task; activation of cognitive rules and methods; belief in the possibilities of thinking; attempt to solve tasks more efficiently. [2; 64]

These functions are interrelated. The first function is due to the fact that children develop ideas about the purpose of the activity. As they get older, they learn to apply certain ways to different situations. Gradually, students develop ideas about cognitive processes. They understand that in order to memorize the material, the teacher needs to listen carefully and remember it. When a student has a clear idea of these psychological processes, he activates attention in one case and memory in another, depending on the nature of the task. In the process, his skills are gradually increasing; he is looking for new ways to solve the problem. When a student believes in the possibilities of his thinking, he does not shy away from difficulties, even if he fails, he thinks and tries to solve the problem. In this process, his attitude to himself changes. He solves the problem in a hurry, not in a hurry, but in an efficient way.

According to P. Massen, J. Kencer, J. Kogan and A. Houston, these functions develop to some extent in all children. However, their upbringing has a significant impact on their level of development. Students with well-organized meta-cognitive functions solve teaching (cognitive) tasks in a planned and purposeful way. These features are a prerequisite for successful training. They need to be developed by all means. The urgency of the issue must be understood in all scientific and methodological terms, and systematic work must be done at school in this area. [2; 65]

Scientific novelty of the research

Various classifications of intellectual knowledge, skills and habits included in the content standards of the learning process adequate to the emerging educational space are given, peculiarities of their formation in students are revealed, effective ways of learning are presented.

Theoretical significance of the research

Different classifications of components of content standards - intellectual knowledge, skills and habits, which are not sufficiently explained (manifested as a "theoretical gap") in the interpretations of the learning

process adequate to the emerging educational space, are given specific features of their formation in students, considerations of effective ways of learning system-structure "on the basis of a dialectical approach.

Practical significance of the research

The novelty of the research will have a positive impact on the formation of intellectual knowledge, skills and habits in students, which are the main components of content standards in the practical activities of educators, the elimination of shortcomings.

The result

1) Knowledge, skills and habits are among the components of the content standards of education adequate to the emerging educational space;

2) There are different classifications of intellectual knowledge, skills and habits, which are the main components of content standards, there are peculiarities of their formation in students, effective ways of learning;

3) Məzmun standartlarının əsas komponentləri olan intellektual bilik, bacarıq və vərdişlərin müxtəlif təsnifatlarına, onların şagirdlərdə formalaşmasının xüsusiyyətlərinə, təlimin səmərəli yollarına diqqət yetirməklə təlimin təşkili və idarə edilməsində bir sıra çatışmazlıqları aradan qaldırmaq olar.

References

1. Abbasov A.N., Mammadzade R.R., Mammadli I.A. Pedagogy: Muntahabat (textbook for universities). Baku, "Mutarjim", 2021, p.111-115.
2. Alizade A.A. Psychological problems of modern Azerbaijani school. Baku, "Pedagogy", 2004, p.59-65.
3. Alizade A.A., Alizade H.A., Alizade S.H. Psychopedagogy. Baku, "Ecoprint", 2019, p.9.
4. General psychology. Textbook for the characteristics of pedagogical institutes. (Edited by Professor A.V.Petrovsky). Baku, "Maarif", 1982, p.191-193.
5. Mehdizade M.M. Ways of development of educational process in secondary schools. Baku, "Maarif", 1982, p.259-261.
6. Ibrahimov F.N., Huseynzade R.L. Pedagogy (textbook). Is. Baku, "Mutarjim", 2014, p.447-454.
7. Ibrahimov F.N. Appendices on the basics of optimal ratios of algorithmic and heuristic activity in training. Baku, "Mutarjim", 2021, p.111.
8. Ibrahimov F.N. Teaching methods based on the curriculum model of mathematics in secondary schools (textbook). Baku, "Mutarjim", 2020, p.37-42.
9. Khalilov S.S. Education, training, upbringing. Baku, "Azerbaijan University", 2005, p.257-288.
10. Bogoyavlinsky D.N., Menchinskaya N.A. Psychology of learning at school. Moscow, Publishing House of APN RSFSR, 1960, pp. 110, 300.
11. Menchinskaya N.A. Teaching problems. Moscow, Publishing House of APN RSFSR, 1989, p. 37-39.
12. Onischuk V.A. Types, structure and methodology of the lesson at school. Kyiv, 1976, p. 21.
13. Pedagogy of the school. Edited by Corr. APN USSR G.I. Schukina, 1977, p.259.